

UNITED4Surveillance pilot report - Finland

1. Describe the **aim and objectives** of your pilot study
Please attach the pilot plan drafted prior to start and/or provide the U4S TEAMS link to this document.

The aim of the pilot was to be able to report severe hospitalized cases of influenza, RSV and Covid-19 in Finland using register information. The objective was thus to study how to link the Hospital Care Register (HILMO) and laboratory notification in NIDR, and explore how to define cases to obtain the information on the hospitalizations in a timely and consistent manner using national registers.

2. Describe the expected output prior to start of the pilot

Well-defined and tested surveillance targets for severe Covid-19, Influenza and RSV to be usable also in a long run.

3. Briefly describe the method(s) used

Laboratory notifications for influenza, RSV and Covid-19 reported to National Infectious Disease were linked with national hospitalization register data to find hospitalized severe cases caused by these pathogens. Cases were defined with specific and unspecific coding lists, episode definitions etc. from 2016 onwards.

4. Report the principal finding(s) of your pilot study

It is technically possible to monitor the incidence and disease burden of severe respiratory infections at the national level with up-to-date registers with good coverage.

5. Formulate your main take-away(s) and recommendations of your pilot study and provide rationale(s)

Linking information from several national registers provide a way to monitor incidence of infection and disease burden at the same time. It is important, however, to know how clinical codes and laboratory tests are used in a country for setting up a surveillance based on clinical codes and laboratory findings.

6. Reflect on most relevant limitations and/or challenges (including potential solutions) and the degree of achieving expected output of your pilot study

During this pilot THL went through considerable cut-downs, and what was even more challenging, major re-organization which led to delays. The license to link registers permanently existed only for Covid-19. There was a plan to send hospitalization data back to central laboratories, but that was not possible as lab system renovation is finishing only during the autumn 2025.

7. Did your pilot study contribute to strengthened (inter)national infectious disease surveillance? Why or why not?

Yes. We could not report hospitalizations due to respiratory symptoms before pandemic, and during pandemic, we could only monitor Covid-19. In U4S we learned how severe respiratory infections are coded in Finland, and how laboratory diagnostics are carried out. With these we could define the surveillance targets and link the registers for better surveillance data.

UNITED4Surveillance legal/privacy barriers (template)

1. To what degree did you experience legal/privacy barrier(s) in your pilot study?

No Little Some Large Very large

For piloting , as well as for other ad hoc studies, data can be obtained from the registers with specific one-time licensing , but to keep the registers linked permanently requires major adjustments in legislations in Finland.

2. If so, please provide a detailed example(s) on the experienced legal/privacy barrier(s) in your pilot study.

See above. In our U4S pilot, which was only considering respiratory infections, we also aimed to pilot how to proceed to other severe infections. This is continued in the Direct Grant funded FinSurveillance.

3. How did you cope with and/or solve the experienced legal and/or privacy barrier within your pilot study? If not, what is your suggestion to solve this legal/privacy barrier(s) in the future?

To change the legislations, we primarily started negotiations with the lawyers in THL. Thereafter we have proceeded to layers in the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health and with the Data Protection Ombudsman in Finland. The Ministry is presently updating the Communicable Disease Act, and we were able to join the working group to make sure linking the registers permanently, in the near future, would be allowed.